
Data-driven modeling and simulation

Version 1
Deliverable 3.2

Project title: Dynamic Mobility Nudge: Shaping sustainable urban mobility behaviour with real-time, user generated and public open data

Project acronym: DyMoN

Project duration: 05/2021 – 04/2024

Project number: 886495

Work package/Task: WP3

Project website: <https://dymon.eu>

Authors: Joakim Munkhammar, Uppsala University, SE
Mahmoud Shepero, Uppsala University, SE
Claudia Luger-Bazinger, Salzburg Research, AT
Dana Kaziyeva, University of Salzburg, Z_GIS, AT

URBAN EUROPE

This project has received funding in the framework of the Joint Programming Initiative Urban Europe.

Document Versions

Version	Date	Changes	Author/s
V1.1	1.12.2022	Preparation of documents content, filling in official details and chapters. Introduction, simulation modelling, nudging modelling proposal, results.	Joakim Munkhammar, Mahmoud Shepero

Table of content

Administrative Information	4
Purpose of the document.....	5
Executive Summary.....	5
1 Introduction	6
2 Original simulation model.....	6
3 Nudging utility function	7
4 Results	8
4.1 The initial nudging simulations	8
4.2 The final nudging simulations	9
5 Conclusions	13
6 References.....	14

Administrative Information

Basic information on the DyMoN project and the present deliverable:

Project title	Dynamic Mobility Nudge: Shaping sustainable urban mobility behaviour with real-time, user generated and public open data
Project coordinator	Salzburg Research Forschungsgesellschaft mbH (SRFG), Salzburg, Austria; project coordinator: Dr. Claudia Luger-Bazinger
Project partners	University of Salzburg, Department of Geoinformatics, Austria Trafficon – Traffic Consultants GmbH, Germany Uppsala University, Department of Civil and Industrial Engineering and Built Environment, Sweden Sustainability InnoCenter, Sweden Ecollective, Sweden
Funding	JPI Urban Europe: ERA-NET Cofund Urban Accessibility and Connectivity (ENUAC) Funding is being provided by the Austrian Research Promotion Agency (FFG) for the Austrian project partners, Energimyndigheten (Sweden) for the Swedish project partners, Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung (BMBF) for the German project partner.
Project nr.	886495
Duration	05/2021 – 04/2024
Webpage	https://dymon.eu/
Deliverable number	D 3.2
Deliverable title	Data-driven modeling and simulation
Authors	Joakim Munkhammar Mahmoud Shepero Claudia Luger-Bazinger Dana Kaziyeva
Version & status	Version 1.0
Date	20 December 2022

Purpose of the document

This document summarizes the data-driven simulation modeling on mobility and the effect on nudges on that, which has been done in the project. The document is part of WP 3 (DyMoN data hub and tools), additionally, it uses results from WP 2 (Repository of nudging methods and content). It will further inform WP 5 (Project evaluation and impact assessment) for estimating potential impact of project results and of nudging influencing mobility choices.

Executive Summary

This deliverable summarizes the simulation results of mobility simulations in the city of Salzburg, and model results regarding attempts to make nudging-model out of this. The simulations show the effect of nudging on the time of mobility and the utility cost of this mobility. The report also presents a novel idea regarding a nudging-based utility function that would controllably reward changing from car to bike for travels.

1 Introduction

Simulations of mobility by different modes are important to be able to understand the impact of nudges influencing mobility choices. In this deliverable, modeling attempts to estimate the effects of nudging on mobility are presented. Also a nudging-based utility function that would controllably economically reward changing from car to bike usage is presented. The nudging modeling developed here was based on published results in [1,2], where the model was built in the GAMA platform [3], and the model developed for this delivery was developed in MATSim. For information on the basis of MATSim, including its built-in functions and original settings, see [3].

2 Original simulation model

The model in this report is based on the Salzburg bicycle model. This section includes a short summary of this Salzburg bicycle model, which is an agent-based model. This is also referred to as the base model in this document. The base model was developed at University of Salzburg and published in [1,2], and its purpose is to simulate highly disaggregated traffic flows of cyclists over one day at a regional scale. Despite the focus on bicycling traffic, the mode choice includes car, car passenger, public transport, walk and bicycle. The basic idea of the model is to dynamically generate activities and trips characterized by activity duration, departure time, transport mode, route etc based on probability distributions. The distributions and behavioral assumptions are derived from mobility surveys and reports.

The modelled agents, or persons, move on a map (here a Salzburg map) to reach randomly chosen locations that match their trip purposes, e.g., workplace if their next activity is work. Firstly, trip purpose or activity type is selected based on the distribution of probabilities dependent on their employment status and the number of carried out activities within a day. Accordingly, it is less likely to have “work” as his/her 6th activity of the day than as 2nd activity of the day.

In the next step, a starting time is sampled for the next activity from a distribution. As regards the model developed here, depending on the activity type, agents choose a certain facility location to go to independently from the reasonable reachable distances characterized by mode. Thus, facilities are chosen at random, which means that travels across the entire city are possible. The travelling mode is finally chosen based on a distribution which is parameterized by the activity type.

The day ends for a person if their next sampled activity is “none”, or if the person performed 7 activities, or if limited by current time as the start time distribution does not include any further departures for specific activity type. For example, a person samples activity “school” as the next activity at 15:00, however, the probability to start school activity after 15:00 is zero according to the distribution. In this case, this person cannot perform the sampled next activity, i.e., “school”, but instead is assumed to go home and finish its daily travels.

Upon converting the model from GAMA to MATSim, a utility function had to be set in MATSim. This utility function has unit Euro, and is the intended cost associated with the activity or transportation. For the initial simulations, a “nudging-enhancing utility function” for controllable transportation behavior change was developed and used, and for the final simulations the built-in utility function in MATSim was used. The

model was based on that the function in MATSim was minimized for all, see the original documentation on MATSim for that [3]. This utility function, denoted S , was based on the cost for travel, that is, the cost of the travel time if it could have been replaced with work.

3 Nudging utility function

The nudging-enhancing utility function for MATSim was developed in this project and presented at the DyMoN consortium meeting in May 2022 in Salzburg. The utility function is here defined in terms of economic gains (here € as a currency is needed) for each individual. This new type of “nudging-enhanced utility function” would controllably reward changing from car to bike. Formally, the main assumption was to define an alternate utility function which controllably rewarded activities and punished traveling. The utility function of an agent, i.e. a single person, in MATSim is represented as:

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^N S_{trip,i} + \sum_{i=1}^N S_{act,i}, \quad (1)$$

where S is the daily score, subscript i is for agent i , S_{trip} is the score based on traveling during this weather condition and using this transport mode, usually is negative; and S_{act} is the score of the activity. The trips were then suggested to be scored according to:

$$S_{trip,i} = \begin{cases} -100 - 10t_{trip,i}, & \text{if trip mode is car} \\ 40 - 10t_{trip,i}, & \text{if trip mode is bicycle} \\ 0, & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $t_{trip,i}$ (hour) is the trip duration. The activities were then suggested to be scored according to:

$$S_{act,i} = \begin{cases} 10t_{act,i}, & \text{if activity is work} \\ 0, & \text{if activity is home} \\ 30t_{act,i}, & \text{else} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $t_{act,i}$ (hour) is the duration of the activity. Work in eq. (3) includes the activities workplace, business, school, and university. The parameters in equations (2) and (3) are guessed parameters, i.e., there is no source that states recommended parameters, but they were set based on the assumption of reducing the car use. This utility function was used in the initial nudging simulation, see results in Section 4.1.

It is also the case that MATSim appears to use experience-guessed or recommended parameters for their own scoring function. The developers of MATSim recommend these values for the parameters based on their previous work experience. Based on this the built-in utility function in MATSim was used in the final nudging simulation, presented in results Section 4.2.

4 Results

4.1 The initial nudging simulations

Using the MATSim model, trips for the whole population of Salzburg, that is, 187 475 inhabitants, were simulated to use car as the mode of transport. A second simulation was made to assume that 20% of the population were successfully nudged to take bike instead. Histograms of the utility function scores for these sampled trips are shown in Figure 1, first (top) without any nudging, then assuming nudging (bottom). In the nudging case the assumption was that 20% of the inhabitants follow a nudge to switch from car to bicycle. The differences can be noticed in the negative values of the histograms and in the mean value difference of the utility scoring over the day. All simulations were made over one weekday with minute resolution.

Figure 1. Simulation output statistics of the scoring function. A histogram of the individual daily utility function scores is shown in the top subfigure. The bottom subfigure shows a histogram of the simulation output where it was assumed that 20% of the inhabitants swapped their car travels for bicycle travels. Notice the decrease in the negative scores. Average utility score before nudges (top) was €569.5 and after nudges (bottom) became €610.5, which increases the mean economic gain for the agents.

A thermal image of road usage in Salzburg, obtained from the simulations, is shown in Figure 2. Please note that this simulation did not include public transport, only biking and car usage.

Figure 2: Thermal map of the road usage in Salzburg from MATSim simulation of 80% car and 20% bike travels over 24 hours.

4.2 The final nudging simulations

Based on feedback from Joakim Munkhammar and Claudia Luger-Bazinger in August 2022, a new simulation with nudges was performed. One suggestion was to simulate two cases using MATSim and its default scoring parameters. In case 1, all people use car, and in case 2 all people switch to bicycle. The task was to compare the scores between the two cases. Another idea was to simulate a normal distribution of modes and assume a certain percentage — for example 30% — of the population were nudged to switch their modes from car to bicycle. For these nudged people, it was assumed that they follow the nudge, i.e., switch their car trips to bicycle. In these simulations, as opposed to the initial simulations, the agents were forced to change behavior, and the associated utility function (and other measures) was estimated from there. Figure 3 presents a schematic sketch of the idea of the simulation.

Figure 3. A diagram representing the simulation procedure of the nudges in the final simulation model.

The implementation of the Salzburg bicycle model was used to generate daily plans for all Salzburg inhabitants — the original plans in [2]. These plans used all travel modes following the distribution of mode choice used in the bicycle model. This distribution depended on the trip purpose — as was the case in the base model. As the next step, nudging of a certain percentage of the population to switch their car trips to bicycle trips was performed. In total 25%, 33%, 50%, 67%, 75%, and 100% of switching from car to bike was simulated. The assumption was that these people would accept the nudges and thereby change their plans, and these new plans are here called nudged plans. As a measure of the simulation output, in terms of impact of nudges from MATSim, comparison statistics were performed.

Figure 4 presents the distribution of scores obtained by MATSim for the simulated cases. Negative scores are due to the fact that MATSim punishes users from performing several short-duration activities during the day. More formally stated, MATSim attaches negative scores to the activities which are shorter than the typical duration for this type of activity, e.g., working for less than 8 hours will have negative score. Negative scores for activities occur in MATSim when durations are shorter than expected, and MATSim will attempt to improve the score by changing the duration of activities. MATSim will change the starting or the ending time or both for this person, such that the work duration gets close to 8 hours. This feature was disabled in MATSim because (a) the base model was used to generate the daily activities, i.e., daily plans of each person and (b) the aim was to isolate the scores due to nudges, the different travelling modes.

This means that no change was made to make MATSim change the durations of activities, i.e., by changing the starting times, as this would disable the comparison between the various nudges. In other words, the plans generated by the original implementation of base model were used in all comparisons as the base model did not take into account typical activity durations in MATSim. In Figure 6, the duration spent travelling in the various simulated cases is presented. In Table 1, the resulting

utility function output from each level of “forced” transportation mode change is shown. This indicates an increase in cost (and thus payoff) for changing from car to bike from 0-50%. This means that there is an incentive already in the standard settings of MATSim to change from car to bike in up to 50% of travels in the city.

Figure 4. Histogram of MATSim scores for the simulated plans. Mean values are presented in Table 1.

Figure 5. Histograms of travelling durations for the simulated plans. Mean values are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Average score Euro per person and mean traveling duration (hr:minute/person/day).

Nudged percentage	Score (€)	Travelling duration
Original plans	48.8	02:59
25%	52.3	02:57
33%	52.5	02:58
50%	52.6	03:01
67%	52.0	03:04
75%	51.7	03:05
100%	50.6	03:10

It is perhaps challenging to notice even the differences between the most extreme cases in Figures 4 and 5 (100% nudged case and the original plan case). Therefore, as an added quantified metric, the mean distance and duration per person and day are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Average distance travelled per day and person (km/day/person) using the various modes and nudging percentages. Travelling time (hr:minute/day/person) is presented between parentheses. It is important to highlight here that differences only occur between the car and bicycle columns. This is because nudges — and thereby rows — change car trips to become bicycle ones.

Nudged %	Bus	Car	Bicycle	Walk	Car passenger
Original plan	3.96 (00:12)	9.56 (00:16)	5.71 (00:19)	06:24 (02:04)	1.39 (00:02)
25%	3.96 (00:12)	6.81 (00:11)	7.55 (00:26)	06:24 (02:04)	1.39 (00:02)
33%	3.96 (00:12)	5.95 (00:09)	8.28 (00:29)	06:24 (02:04)	1.39 (00:02)
50%	3.96 (00:12)	4.43 (00:06)	9.60 (00:34)	06:24 (02:04)	1.39 (00:02)
67%	3.96 (00:12)	2.95 (00:04)	11.00 (00:34)	06:24 (02:04)	1.39 (00:02)
75%	3.96 (00:12)	2.21 (00:03)	11.68 (00:42)	06:24 (02:04)	1.39 (00:02)
100%	3.96 (00:12)	0 (00:00)	13.78 (00:49)	06:24 (02:04)	1.39 (00:02)

5 Conclusions

In this project part, the effect of nudging on traffic was investigated with simulation tools. A form of nudging-enhanced utility function for MATSim was developed and tested for Salzburg simulations, indicating change in behavior. Secondly, the original settings of MATSim were used, but with agents forced to change from car to bike, and output statistics from this were estimated.

As the first conclusion, it was possible to simulate the travels of bike, car and public transport using a MATSim-model developed based on the base model. Second, a “nudging enhancing utility function” that would control agents to change from car to bike was tested for 20% changing from car to bike, and it did increase the payoff for the agents.

Third, simulations were made using the MATSim built-in utility function with the addition that X percent of agents were forced to change from car to bike. The result showed that from zero to 50% changing from car to bike resulted in a cost increase in the utility function, which implied that there was a payoff for changing from car to bike in up to 50% of the travels in the city. It was also shown that the utility payoff was lower for increasing the share taking bike compared to car over 50%. In order to increase further from that point, the utility payoff has to change in these simulations.

The nudging-enhancing utility function was presented as a possible solution to make a controllable economic gain from switching transport mode, but the interpretation of it in terms of societal and economic sense was left as an open problem. One possible interpretation would be that the city needs to economically compensate the difference between the utility functions for people to change modes of transport (beyond 50%, which is already incentivized in the MATSim original setting simulations). If so, then nudging would be a way to possibly save some part of that economic compensation, as nudging by definition would imply some form of voluntary non-economic transition from car usage to bike usage.

The nudging utility function, as was designed in this project, was based on monetary costs for agents. It is possible that it could also be based on some other motivator, for example climate impact or personal well-being.

A complete test of this in a real life scenario would be advantageous, at least in perhaps attempting to define the nudging-adapted utility function.

6 References

- [1] Gudrun Wallentin and Martin Loidl. Agent-based bicycle traffic model for Salzburg city. *GI Forum J. Geogr. Inf. Sci.*, 2015:558–566, 2015.
- [2] Dana Kaziyeva, Martin Loidl, and Gudrun Wallentin. Simulating spatiotemporal patterns of bicycle flows with an agent-based model. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 10(2):88, 2021. doi:10.3390/ijgi10020088.
- [4] Kay W Axhausen, Andreas Horni, and Kai Nagel. *The multi-agent transport simulation MATSim*. Ubiquity Press, 2016.
- [4] Patrick Taillandier, Benoit Gaudou, Arnaud Grignard, Quang-Nghi Huynh, Nicolas Marilleau, Philippe Caillou, Damien Philippon, and Alexis Drogoul. Building, composing and experimenting complex spatial models with the GAMA platform. *Geoinformatica*, 23(2):299–322, 2019.